

NCCR 2021

Research Poster Competition

GUIDELINES FOR NCCR 2021 RESEARCH POSTER COMPETITION

[SUBMIT YOUR ABSTRACT NOW](#)

1. Eligibility Criteria

- a. Abstract should be based on original research and should NOT have been presented / published at any national or international scientific conferences.
- b. At least one of the authors of the poster MUST register for the conference.
- c. Participants may submit more than ONE abstract.
- d. Abstracts must be submitted in ENGLISH.
- e. Studies conducted in Ministry of Health facilities or using Ministry of Health data must submit NMRR ID and MREC approval letter with their abstract.
- f. All clinical studies will be considered. This include observational or interventional studies, cross sectional surveys, case series, and case report
- g. The Scientific Committee will review and reserve the right to decide on the acceptance of abstracts for poster presentation.

2. Submission Guidelines

- a. All abstracts must be submitted online at <https://tinyurl.com/nccr-abstract>.
- b. Hardcopy submissions will not be accepted. For any problem with abstract submission, kindly contact the NCCR Abstract Secretariat at nccrabstracts@gmail.com.
- c. Abstracts must be submitted by 11.59pm of 30th June 2021. Late submissions or incomplete abstracts will not be accepted.
- d. The Secretariat will notify participants regarding the results of their submission by 30th July 2021.
- e. Payment for conference registration should reach the Organizer by 30th July 2021.

3. Abstract Format

- a. The structured abstract should not exceed 250 word limits and include the following sections: Introduction, Methodology, Results and Discussion / Conclusion.
- b. Author(s)' name must be written in FULL. Do not include professional title or degrees. List any institutional affiliation, state and country. Please make sure all authors contributed significantly to the research project.
- c. Abstract title must be in Title Case, e.g. "Cardiovascular Problems in Community Settings". Title should be brief and clearly indicate the content of the abstract.
- d. Do not include graphs, tables, illustrations or references in the abstract.
- e. Abbreviations must be defined by placing it in parenthesis after the full word, the first time it appears.
- f. Use numerals to represent numbers except when beginning a sentence.

4. Dr Wu Lien-Teh Research Awards

a. Young Investigator Awards

- Only original work that has not been published or presented will be considered.
- The first author must be the presenting author and should be 40 years of age or below.
- 20 abstracts with the highest grades will be shortlisted for the Young Investigator Award, and the Top 5 will present as oral presentations during the conference.
- First place winner will receive RM1,000 with a medal, followed by RM800 for second place, RM600 for third place, and RM300 for consolation prizes.
- Each winner will also receive a certificate of achievement.
- Judges' decisions are final. No correspondence would be entertained.

b. Best Poster Awards

- The First prize winner will be awarded RM500 with a medal, followed by RM350 for second place, RM250 for third place, and RM100 for consolation prizes.
- Each winner will receive a certificate of achievement.
- Judges' decisions are final. No correspondence would be entertained.

5. Poster Display and Presentation

- a. Poster must be prepared in the following format: vertical A0 size (90cm width x 120cm height).
- b. Posters (in PDF format) of the accepted submissions must be emailed to the NCCR Abstract Secretariat at nccrabstracts@gmail.com by 12noon of 8th August 2021.
- c. Late submission of the poster will not be entertained.
- d. All late submissions will be deemed as withdrawal from the competition.

6. For Enquiries, please contact:

- a. NCCR Abstract Secretariat (Email: nccrabstracts@gmail.com)

7. Some Do's and Don'ts

- a. Do use the template provided.
- b. Do follow the abstract and poster format.
- c. Do keep your abstracts limited to 250 words.
- d. Do use graphics, colour, or photos to enhance visual presentation of your poster.
- e. Do not miss the deadlines.
- f. Do not let the design of your poster overshadow the content.

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